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Conflict Resolution between Heads and Teachers: The Case of 4 Schools in Masvingo Zimbabwe

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Research Article

Conflict Resolution between Heads and Teachers: The Case of 4 Schools in Masvingo Zimbabwe

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ABSTRACT

The study sought to establish causes of conflict amongst primary school heads and teachers and how such conflicts could be resolved in Masvingo, Zimbabwe. The study also sought to establish teachers' perceptions of conflict, and their preference of conflict arbitrators. Sixteen purposively selected teachers from 4 schools responded to questionnaire items in this survey. The major findings of the study were that conflicts exist in most schools as heads and teachers conflict with each other over unequal distribution/allocation of resources and grapevine or gossips. It was also established that teachers and heads frequently conflict and most teachers were not satisfied with the ways in which problems were resolved. They preferred the District Education Officers (D.E.Os) to resolve their conflicts with the School Heads. The study recommends that School heads should ensure equitable and transparent distribution of resources at schools and workshops on conflict and conflict resolution should be mounted for school stakeholders including heads, teachers and school development committees/associations.

KEYWORDS School Head; Subordinates; Supervisor; Attitude; Disciplinary Committee, Negotiation

INTRODUCTION

In our day to day lives, there is no single day that passes without people talking about negotiation. Negotiation has become a chorus notion in every household. This simply indicates its importance as a means of solving problems. As people are enlightened more about their rights and how they are sometimes abused; conflicts resolutions become necessary. But negotiations come in as a result of conflict. Conflict, for Nyamajiwa (2000, p. 3), can be defined as, "the opposition of individuals", or groups' interest, opinions or purpose". It can be between individuals, groups, parties or countries. However, most conflict situations require negotiation whenever they occur. In order to formulate an effective solution, it is essential that all factors which give rise to the conflict situation are carefully identified and explored. Nyamajiwa (2000) has identified some causes or sources of conflict within an organization. These include inadequate information, role conflict/collision, and differences in goals, values, and competition for limited resources, responsibility, personnel, space, tools and equipment, access to superiors. In an organization such as a school, a number of these sources of conflict could be applicable to school heads and class teachers. Almost every day we hear of cases where teachers and heads conflict over issues that concern their practices and district offices are inundated with reports of teachers and heads on collision paths. In most cases, unresolved conflicts result in communication breakdown affecting the smooth running of the school. In other instances heads physically fight with teachers over certain issues. Such situations disturb the tone and climate of the school and ultimately the performance of both teachers and pupils is negatively affected. Perturbed by these circumstances, the study sought to establish the major sources of these conflicts and examine the frequency or occurrences of the negotiations between school heads and teachers. In addition the study will seek to establish teachers' preference of who should mediate or resolve the conflicts.

Conceptual framework

Conflict can be perceived as the opposition of an individual's ideas by another part. Kreps (1990) views conflict process by which individuals express and negotiate their differences. Furthermore, Kreps (1990) asserts that conflict is an expressed struggle between two or more competing positions held by one or more individuals usually based on

incompatible beliefs, ideas or goals. Conflict arises whenever perceived or real interest collide (Hanson, 1991, p. 285). The collision can result from a divergence in organizational goals, personal ambitions, group loyalties, departmental budget demands on scarce resources, ethnic expectations and demands and so forth. Thus, in a school, conflict can arise from divergence in expectations of scarce resources like accommodation, classrooms, instructional resources, such as chalk, manila, and so on. Conflict can also occur due to divergence in terms of ideas, especially when a teacher's idea may not coincide with that of the head.

Hanson (1991) argues that conflict and stress result from interactions within and between formal organization levels. Thus, conflict is inevitable in any organization either positively or negatively; constructively or retrogressively. Hanson (ibid) classifies conflict into different categories namely intra-role, inter-role, intra-departmental, intra-organisational, intrapersonal and interpersonal.

Hanson (1991) states that intra-role conflict results when various members in a role set simultaneously and legitimately make differing demands on a single role. He posits that if the complexity and specialisation is great, the degree of interdependence and need for role conformity will also be great. Intra role conflict at a school can occur when teachers claim that instructional materials are too difficult for a grade level, some teachers claim that they are too easy and so forth. Inter-role conflict is the simultaneous occurrence of two (or more) sets of pressures such that compliance with one would make more difficult complaints with the other (Hanson, 1991). This type of conflict typically occurs when one individual holds several different roles that make competing demands.

Intradepartmental conflict occurs when members of the same formal unit cannot agree on an important issue. For example, when Mathematics teachers cannot agree on whether to introduce computers into the classroom instructional process, the outcome can be considerable turbulence. Besides, intra-organisational conflict is often characterized by clashes that transcend hierarchical levels, for instance, teachers complaining to the District Education Officers about unrealistic demands on their time. Hanson (1991) perceives unfair distribution and unfair deadlines as the major sources of this conflict. Intrapersonal conflict is caused by troublemakers. Hanson (1991) identifies troublemakers as disturbed people who have not developed satisfying and healthy patterns with society. At a school the head can encounter intrapersonal conflict when there is poor time management, underestimation or over estimation of skills and assigned tasks that do not match goals, interest, values or abilities. Additional causes are the inability to say no to requests, a lack of self-confidence and lack of control.

Interpersonal conflict is perceived as the most frequent in schools. It concerns the quality of interactions between two or more teachers. This can be due to severe personality differences between teachers. Interpersonal conflict can emanate from the personal motives of those involved. Conflict between individuals and groups, is perceived by Hanson (1991) as developing when two members in a group normally good friends normally find themselves seeking promotion to a single job. Group conflict can occur when an individual teacher resists the influence of a group to conform to certain agreed practices. The lack of acceptance leads to conflict and deviant behavior.

Sources of conflict

Nyamajiwa (2000:4) cites several sources of conflict viz; goal incompatibility, unavailability of resources, performance expectations and organizational structures. Goal incompatibility occurs when there is a lack of agreement concerning the direction of evaluating task accomplishment. This source of conflict is said to be the most frequent in an organization. In an organization such as the school, individual teachers may bring with them different time and goal orientations that may create a state of high differentiation.

Further to that, Nyamajiwa (2000, p .4) recognises that conflict within an organization can be caused by competition for limited resources. He asserts that at a school for instance books and furniture are mostly in short supply. Another source of conflict is activity or performance of one person in a group that affects the subsequent performance of other members. In other words, one member's work cannot begin until another member provides some needed information. In many organizations, the structure or role is a potential source of conflict. There can be function conflict in a functional structure and division conflict in a product structure. In a school, this type of conflict can be seen in the relationship between the head and the teachers. The problem lies in the view points of each member and their roles in schools.

Several strategies have been suggested for resolving conflict. These range from avoidance, non-attention, physical separation, limited interaction, compromise and confrontation (Hanson, 1996; Rahim 1992). Non attention refers to a situation whereby the Head of the department totally avoids or ignores the dysfunction situation. Because the sources of conflict are not identified by this method it is likely that the situation may continue or worsen with time.

Physical separation actually involves moving conflicting groups physically apart, from each other, the rationale being that if the groups cannot interact, conflict will diminish. However, this strategy will adversely affect the overall effectiveness of the organization. Alder and Rodman (1985) alluded to indirect aggression as similar to physical separation. Limited interaction is not an all-inclusive strategy; conflicting parties are permitted to interact on a limited

basis. Interactions are permitted generally only under formal situations such as a meeting at which a strict agenda is followed.

Compromise reflects splitting the difference or giving up something to get something (Hanson, 1996). Compromise is generally effective when the conflicting groups are relatively equal in strength. In situations where one of the groups is significantly stronger or in a better position than the second group, a compromise strategy would not work because the stronger group would hold out for a one-sided solution. Rahim (1992) asserts that in a compromise response there is an intermediate position between concern for self and concern for others. It incorporates some elements from each of the other responses. The compromising person is less integrating, less dominating, less obliging, and less avoiding than non-compromising persons. Each person sacrifices something to achieve at least a partial resolution of the conflict, which may not be satisfactory to either party.

Confrontation differs from other conflict tactics in that the sources of conflict are generally identified and discussed (Hanson, 1996). Emphasis is put on the attainment of the common interest of the conflicting groups. The assumption underlying this strategy is that the exchanged personnel can learn about the other group and communicate their impressions to their original group. Rahim(1992) refers to this strategy as the integrating or the "I win/you win" response. He argues that it is the best outcome to the conflict and people using this style believe themselves to be important, and they believe the other people in the conflict are important, too. Behaviors include expressing feelings, beliefs, and ideas openly and honestly to others (whether positive or negative), listening to others, and responding to their comments in a clear, firm voice. Each of the conflict strategies is appropriate in some situations and in- appropriate in others. People who handle conflict effectively ascertain the unique, characteristics of the conflict situation they are in and choose the most appropriate to use. Often, individuals however grow accustomed to using one primary conflict strategy and develop hard to change propensities towards conflict.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers employed the descriptive method to gather data. According to Mwiri and Wahiu (1995, p. 21) a survey can collect data on what people say. Hence, in this study it was considered the best in collecting data about attitudes and views of people. Surveys also permit one to obtain information simply by observing the events taking place at that moment. Four schools were purposively selected from the sixteen schools in Zimuto area, Masvingo North. These schools were chosen on the basis of their proximity to the researchers. The target population comprised four heads and forty-eight teachers from the four respective schools. The final sample comprised four heads and sixteen teachers conveniently sampled. These responded to the researchers' interviews and questionnaires respectively. The collected data were expressed as percentages for analysis.

Presentation and Discussion of data

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by marital status

Marital status	Number	Percentage %
Single	2	12.5
Married	13	81.25
Separated	-	-
Widowed	1	6.25
Total	16	100

The data revealed that the majority of the respondents (81.25%) were married and only a few were single (12.5%). This could imply that the respondents were mature and might have encountered and resolved conflicts at their homes. This composition might assist the researchers to establish the causes of conflict from teachers who are mature and not frustrated by either death or absence of a spouse. The few respondents who were either widowed or single were also necessary in this study as their view would provide balanced perceptions of the problem under study. There was gender balance – fifty percent males and fifty percent females.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by age

Age(years)	No.	%
Below 20 years		
21-25	1	6.25
26-30	3	18.75
31-35	8	50
36-40	4	25
41-45		
46-50		
50+		
Total	16	100

Table 3: Respondents' Academic qualifications

Qualification	No.	%
Standard 6	0	0
Zimbabwe Junior Certificate(ZJC)	0	0
O'Level	11	69.75
A' Level	5	31.25
First Degree	0	0
Total	16	100

The majority of the respondents were O'Level (ordinary level)certificate holders with a few A/Level (advanced level)certificate holders. Ordinary certificate is the basic qualification for anyone to enroll for a teacher training course. Standard 6 and ZJC were long been phased out .None of the respondents were academic degree holders. The level of education of someone may contribute to his/her contact with others.

Table 4: Respondents by Professional Qualifications

Qualification	No.	%
Certificate in Education	2	12.5
Diploma in Education	11	68.75
Bachelor of Education Degree	3	18.75
Total	16	100

Table 5: Respondents' working experience

Working Experience(in years)	No.	%
0-5	5	31.25
6-10	7	43.75
11-15	4	25
16-20	0	0
21+	0	0
Total	16	100

All the respondents were in the range 21-40years old. This is the most active and innovative age group. As for their academic and professional qualification, all respondents were qualified teachers with either a Certificate in Education (68%) or Diploma in Education (13%).Nineteen percent of them were degree holders. Their qualifications implied that the respondents were not novice in the profession. The majority (79%) of them had working experience varying from 6-15 years. In Zimbabwe these are considered to be senior teachers who can apply for any promotional post, such as for deputy head.

Sources of conflict in schools

The majority of the teacher respondents (69%) indicated in affirmation that school heads are the sources of conflict and only thirty one percent said no. This was however contrary to the Heads' who view teachers as the major source of conflict. Respondents who indicated that they had at times disagreed with the head cited various issues over they had been at loggerheads with the Head. The majority of the respondents cited the unequal allocation of resources as the major source of conflict. The resources range from classrooms, accommodation and stationery. A few respondents (13%) cited other sources such as gossips and grapevine whilst only one indicated class allocation. This implies that most teachers conflict with school heads over issues which matter in their day to day execution of duty particularly when fairness and equity in terms of distribution are overridden.

On *who* usually causes conflict, sixty two percent indicated school administrators as conflict causers with only forty percent indicating teachers as the culprit. The school administrators range from the teacher in charge (T.I.C), senior teacher, deputy head and school head. This implies that every person at a school has the potential of causing conflict and that most conflicts in an organization emanate from power struggles or role conflict.

Respondents were also asked to indicate the *frequency* of these conflicts. One respondent indicated that Heads and teachers conflict daily, Twenty five percent indicated that they conflict weekly and thirty seven percent indicated that barely a month passes without conflict. In general the data indicate that conflicts are rampant at schools. However, the frequency varies from school to school.

Respondents were also asked to indicate whether teachers conflict with each other and the frequency of conflicts if ever they were there. About 60% of the respondents indicated that teachers usually conflict with each other. The conflicts usually occur on monthly basis. However, about 40% of the respondents indicated that teachers rarely conflict with each other. Some of those who indicated that teachers usually conflict with each cited unfair class/subject allocation as sources of conflicts. A few others indicated allocation of duties and unequal distribution of learning and teaching resources.

Responding to the question on who resolves conflict between teachers, sixty-three percent of the respondents indicated that the Head usually resolves conflicts between teachers. Two (13%) indicated the deputy head and senior teachers and only twenty-five percent reflected the disciplinary committee. On who resolves conflicts between teachers and School heads half (50%) of the respondents indicated that the Head does that while about forty- six percent cited the disciplinary committee. Only one respondent cited the school development committee. The data imply that most conflicts between teachers are resolved at school level.

As to their preference of conflict resolution between teachers and Heads, four (25%) respondents preferred the School head, 2 (13%) preferred the Deputy Head and 3 (19%) preferred the disciplinary committee. Another small number of the respondents (two) said that they preferred the School Development Committees (S.D.Cs).Thirty-eight percent of the respondents said that they would prefer the D.E.O to resolve their conflicts. The study could not ascertain the reasons for their preference as well as the complexity of the conflict.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that conflict is inexistence in schools as barely a month passes without either the Head conflicting with the teachers or the teachers amongst themselves. Most teacher respondents perceived the School Head as the major source of most conflicts in a school. Most respondents cited conflicts as emanating from unfair distribution of resources such as classrooms, stationery, accommodation as well as classes. The Head as school administrator was seen as perpetrating conflict amongst teachers when he/she exercises unfairness in the allocation/distribution of these resources which in most cases are scarce. This supports Whitaker(1996) who asserts that 30-40% of the School Head 's time is spent on preventing or resolving conflict ,however, many conflicts find their sources in the Head's leadership style as the major source of conflict. Other causes of conflict amongst teachers were rumours or grapevine.

On the other hand, Adhiambo &Samatwa (2011) in a similar study established that causes of conflict between teachers and administration were: academic performance, difference in opinion, negative attitude towards each other, disciplining of students, intimate relationship between teachers and administration, irresponsibility on the part of all the parties, lack of time management and improper lesson planning by teachers. However, the study established that most teachers preferred someone other than the Head, preferably the District Education Officers to resolve conflict particularly where the Head is an interested part. Thus, an integrated or confrontational strategy is the most preferred where both parties resolve the conflict in good faith, devoid of mistrust.

CONCLUSION

From the above findings it was evident that teachers and Heads may conflict over certain issues on daily, weekly and /or monthly basis. Reasons for such conflicts were allocation of classes/classrooms, unfair allocation of teaching and learning resources such as charts and stationery. Rumours and grapevine contribute insignificantly to conflicts. It was also noted that not only teachers and heads conflict but teachers can also conflict with their counterparts. Reasons for conflicts between teachers were the same as for Heads and teachers. Findings also reflected that most conflicts at school are resolved at school level with the School Head playing a conflict resolution role in cases where he/she is involved. It was also evident that most teachers were not satisfied with the way conflicts were resolved at school level, and, hence, preferred an outsider like the D.E.O to resolve their conflicts with the Head.

The study concludes that conflict is an inevitable outcome of human interaction. Allocation and distribution of classes, classrooms and learning and teaching resources are the major sources of conflicts at school. Rumours contribute insignificantly to conflicts between teachers and Heads. Teachers prefer the D.E.Os to School Heads to resolve conflict between teachers and Heads.

Recommendations

From the aforementioned findings and conclusions, the study recommends that:

- Heads and teachers should ensure that there is equity and transparency in the distribution of resources at schools.
- Heads should ensure that there is justice and fairness in resolving conflicts at the school.
- Workshops on conflict resolutions should be mounted for teachers, S.D.C/As and school administrators.
- School authorities (S.D.C/As) should ensure that their institutions have adequate teaching and learning resources.
- The School Heads should enhance effective communication with all stakeholders in the school to minimize causes of conflict.

REFERENCES:

- Adhiambo, R. & Simatwa, M. (2011). Assessment of conflict management and resolution in public secondary schools in Kenya: A case study of Nyakach District. *International Research Journal Vol. 2(4) pp. 1074-1088*
- Adler, R.B. & Rodman, G. (1985). *Understanding Human Communication*. New York: C.B.S. College Publishing.
- Hanson E.M. (1991). *Educational Administration and Organizational Behavior*. Boston: Simon and Schuster Inc
- Johnson, P.E. & Payne J (1997). Power, communicator styles, and conflict management styles: A web of interpersonal constructs for the school principal. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 6, 40–53.
- Kreps, G.L. (1990). *Organisational Communication*. New York: Longman
- Leedy, P.D. (1980). *Practical Research; Planning and Design*. New York: MacMillan
- Nyamajiwa, B.M. (2000). *Communication in Negotiation*. Harare: University of Zimbabwe Centre for Distance Education
- Rahim, M.A. (1992). *Managing Conflict in Organizations*. New York: Praeger.
- Whitaker, K.S. (1996). Exploring causes of principal burnout. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 34, 60–71.